

STAFFORDSHIRE UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF COMPUTING

Dissertation submitted for partial fulfilment of degree

BSc Cyber Security

Machine Learning & IMINT Analysis

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April 2020

Abstract

Machine Learning & IMINT Analysis

This study aims to evaluate how machine learning can be implemented in the field of geospatial intelligence collection as means of analysing high velocity and high volume image data. This study will evaluate a range of machine learning and image analysis techniques through the development of three prototype systems implementing: binary classification, binary object detection, and multi-classification object detection. The prototypes achieved a high level of detection capabilities with the final YOLO darknet model achieving a mAP of 60% on test scene with a GSD < 0.250 .

Abbreviations

DA	Data Augmentation
AP	Average precision
ML	Machine Learning
NN	Neural Network
GIS	Geographic Information Science
mAP	Mean Average Precision
GSD	Ground Sample Distance
GDA	Geospatial Data Analysis
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
SSD	Single Shot Detector
DNN	Deep Neural Network
IMINT	Image Intelligence
R-CNN	Region Based Convolutional Neural Network
SIGINT	Signals Intelligence
FR-CNN	Fast Region Based Convolutional Neural Network

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Introduction

In the age of big data finding new and inventive analytic technologies has become a multi-billion dollar industry, now more than ever data science intersects with multiple different disciplines in the hope of advancing their analytical capabilities with the field of intelligence being no exception. Since its inception, IMINT has become a cornerstone of intelligence gathering with the proliferation of specialised spaceborne earth imaging satellites granting intelligence agencies access to vast amounts of data. The primary challenges of both state and private institutions is how to process data of such high velocity and volume whilst effectively extracting the full richness of said data. This study will evaluate how machine learning has been implemented to challenges these issues and how the technology could be implemented to further advance intelligence collection.

Chapter 1

Study Outline

1.1 Aims Objectives

The aim of this dissertation is to research the use of computer vision technology in IMINT analysis and produce a software artifact capable of performing multi-classification object detection on military aircraft in both satellite and airborne imagery. This study will use opensource datasets for the training and testing of these models and use performance metrics to evaluate the implementation of various deep neural networks. This study will asses various aspect of DNN IMINT analysis to produce an effective solution including the evaluation of data and model optimisation of object detection methodologies.

1.2 Ethics

Refer to submitted declaration

1.3 Risk Assessment

Insignificant risk was posed during this study beyond prolonged exposure to a computer screen and sitting in a desk chair. Regular breaks were taken during this study to mitigate this risk

1.4 Methodology

To begin investigating how computer vision technology could be used for the analysis of IMINT, a robust methodology had to be constructed to test a variety of implementations including but not limited to experimentation with a variety of models, optimisers, and data-sets. To ensure a broad range of approaches to solving the problem had been considered a sequence of prototypes were created. Each prototype focused on testing a specific aspect of computer vision technology to ascertain which approach produced the most effective model. This included testing model performance on limited datasets and a variety of model architectures; this quantitative method allowed for the collection of insightful data on model performance such as validation/test accuracy and mAP. The latter metrics were the primary values by which the performance of the model was assessed as they are a directly observable indication of the model's performance. Testing models with an increasing complexity acts as a form of parallel-reliability testing ensuring the previous conclusions of model performance holds up against more complex but equivalent forms of testing. Before development started, research was conducted into pre-existing approaches to computer vision and object detection/classification, though the emphasis was placed on focusing on research primarily concerned with the intersection of geospatial analysis and machine learning there was considerable value to be gained from researching a broader range of computer vision implementations. This primarily consisted of reading various case studies and research papers that focused on the optimisation of existing object detection algorithms.

A theoretical analysis of computer vision technology would not have been a sufficient enough approach to test the performance of various technological implementations, nor would it have fit the remit of the project proposal. As such, an in-depth development process was constructed to provide practical oversight of all aspects of the software artifact. For a project of this scope agile development was the bests approach as this allowed for sustained research and reflective development. The entirety of the project was separated

into sprints each of which consisted of various development milestones and culminating in the completion of a prototype system.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Computer vision is a broad interdisciplinary field of study that focuses on how computers and mathematical algorithms can be used to produce deep analysis of both image and video data. The available literature is expansive with various supplementary works from a spectrum of disciplines, this study will focus on literature primarily concerned with computer engineering/software development and the associated thematics. The studies on these topics have focused on addressing how to build a computationally effective machine learning model and so this review has been separated into the following areas of study; Data preparation and pre-processing methods for the effective use and manipulation of data, model structure to address the best technological implementation, IMINT technologies, and the application of ML in geospatial data analysis. The reviewed literature spans a range of contexts and domains however this study will focus on the implementation of these technologies in geospatial/IMINT data analysis.

2.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

'Neural network' is a catch-all term used to describe a family of computer models that mimic the human neural system in its ability to learn observed patterns. These models have evolved from a simple single-layer perceptron architecture to far more complex deep-

learning architecture with the introduction of hidden layers, this allowed NN to perform more complex tasks [25] than a shallow linear model. There are many model architectures included in the deep learning category one of which is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), It is widely accepted that CNNs are the most effective model to implement for image processing tasks [23] with wide-ranging success in multiple disciplines including IMINT/geospatial data analysis. A CNN follows a DNN architecture with multiple hidden layers, these hidden layers can have a variety of compositions but will always consist of multiple convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers with 4 main operations; convolution, nonlinearity, pooling, and classification fig 2.1.

Figure 2.1: CNN architecture

Unlike CNNs, traditional NN or MLPs (multilayer perceptrons) are incapable of effectively extracting or recognising image data as they are incapable of learning translation invariances and spatial data is lost during data flattening [14], this causes the semantic relationship between pixel locations to lose value. Additionally, the input layer of an MLP utilises a one-to-one relationship between the perceptrons and the input data. This means each image pixel would be assigned to a singular perceptron causing an exponential increase in the trainable weights within the NN.

2.1.1 Convolutional Layer

Convolutional layers are one of the main components in the first block of a CNN and are characteristic of this form of NN. The convolutional layer is always the first layer in a CNN (input layer excluded) and is responsible for extracting features from an image as well as calculating the label predictions during testing. The neurons within a CNN are arranged into layers with each layer segmented into feature maps. These feature maps share the same weight matrix which is initialised and updates by backpropagation using gradient descent, in essence, they are each tasked with learning the same features [14]. There are 3 key apparatus used during convolution: the filter, the receptive field, and the activation/feature map along with 4 key hyperparameters: the stride, number of filters, the filter size (FxFxD), and the zero-padding.

The receptive field is a matrix representation of the image data to which the filter is being applied, these filters or feature detectors are a matrix of values known as weights that are used to perform an element-wise matrix multiplication successively to the receptive field as shown in 2.2. The size of this filter is dependant on the resolution of the input data and the depth of the image (RGB or greyscale) though smaller filter sizes of an odd dimension are more optimal. Smaller filters allow for more detailed and highly local feature extraction versus larger filters, this does however reduced the filter's ability to learn more general information about the input data as such the filter size can be domain-specific [2].

The optimum number of filters is also domain-specific, though an increased number of filters does increase the number of learnable features this does not directly correlate with model performance as an unnecessary amount of filters can lead to learning saturation. A good practice is to adjust the number of filters following the characteristics and complexity of the input data to optimise the learning process. The size of the stride directly affects the dimensionality of the feature map if a larger stride is chosen a smaller feature map will be created than if a larger stride had been chosen. It is optimal to maintain the same dimensionality when producing a feature map, to do so a zero-padding is applied

to the input matrix this surrounds the input with a layer of pixels with a value of 0, this prevents issues with dimensionality as the feature map passes through each layer. A stride of 1 is often set in CNNs as this defers the responsibility of downsampling to the pooling layers[3].

Figure 2.2: Feature Map

1	1	1	0	0			
0	1	1	1	0			
0	0	1x1	1x0	1x1	4	3	4
0	0	1x0	1x1	0x0	2	4	3
0	1	1x1	0x0	0x1	2	3	4

convolution produces a feature map/intermediate activation [15] representing a learnt feature of the input data that preserves spatial data and by analyzing the significance of local pixel values. Convolution is often illustrated as a 2D operation however convolutions are performed in 3D as images are presented as a 3D matrix comprised of height, width, and depth (RGB) [4]. To perform this operation multiple filters are applied to the input to produce multiple features maps, the deeper into the CNN we progress the more abstract these feature maps become. The initial layers will retain most of the information present within an image by extracting distinct features (e.g. eye, mouth, nose). Deeper layers will extract more abstract features (e.g. edges and shapes) ensuring s the CNN is able to detect labels with both unique or distinct features 2.3.

2.1.2 Pooling Layer

The pooling layer makes up the second component of the first characteristic block of a CNN and often separates the convolutional layers. Both the pooling layer and the convo-

Figure 2.3: Layer Feature Extraction

lutional layers operate in a similar way however the pooling layer is incapable of feature extraction. Pooling layers are used to reduce the spatial resolution of image data using max or average pooling [33]. A key functionality of the pooling layer is the detection of translational invariances in the input data which is a keystone for the performance of image classification CNNs. This allows the CNN to better generalise the input data whilst being able to handle challenging label predictions where vast invariances are present i.e. occlusion, lighting, orientation. A max pooling operation is a sample-based discretization process that aids in preventing overfitting by providing a more abstract representation of spatial data whilst reducing the number of parameters the model has to learn. If for example a max pooling operation were applied to a 4x4 matrix of numerical values (initial input) with a spatial extent hyperparameter of 2x2, the resultant 2x2 matrix would consist of the max values of each region of our input matrix, this is termed down-sampling when applied to image data 2.4

Figure 2.4: Demonstration of max and average pooling operations

In older models these pooling layers would propagate the average of each filter matrix

to the next layer though in more recent models the max value of each filter matrix is propagated referred to as max pooling as this has been found to be more effective for image classification [33]. Faraz Saeedan et al demonstrates that max pooling operations are better at capturing invariances in image data, the importance of which was discussed in section 2.2, this lead to improved generalisation and convergence when compared to other pooling operations. The difference in performance was demonstrated when (LeCun 2004) published there results of a classification task using the NORB dataset which out performed the previous best model by over half a percentage.

2.1.3 Dense/Fully Connected Layer

The fully connected layer or dense layer is not characteristic of a CNN and will always be the final layer of a classification NN as this is the layer that provides the classification capability, this layer is characterised by having full connections to all the activations in the previous layer. The size of this layer (input volume) is dependant on the number of classification the CNN is attempting to predict, so in the case of written numeral these input volume would be 10 (0 - 9). The input of this layer comes from the previous conv or max-pooling layers in the form of a flattened vector of weights which represent class probability. Isolated backpropogation is utilised in the fully connected output layer to update the weights of each output node, these node represent label features which are used to calculate the final classification prediction 2.5.

2.1.4 Activation Functions

Though Deeper NNs provide greater performance convolution is inherently a linear process so to utilise the added benefit of hidden layers non-linearity must be introduced, additional performance issues that are inherent with CNNs such a vanishing or exploding gradients can also be resolved with the introduction of an activation function. Vanishing gradients occur when a pixel value is less than 1, the successive multiplications that occur in the

Figure 2.5: Fully connected layer

hidden layer will cause the gradient to trend to 0. Conversely, if the pixel value is greater than 1 the derivative term will trend towards infinity thus exploding the gradient and skewing the weight matrix [27]. With the introduction of an AF, the output of each convolution layer is constrained to a certain value. A variety of AFs can be implemented in a NN though the best one to choose is domain dependant, as this paper is focused on multi-classification CNNs and IMINT analysis the focus will be on rectified linear unit function (ReLU) and softmax. ReLU was originally proposed by Nair and Hinton [27]) where they implemented ReLU on Restricted Boltzmann machines, consequently, ReLU became the most commonly used AF for deep learning architectures [28]. The primary operation of ReLU is to set a threshold of 0 so that any negative input values are removed by changing them to 0 as given below:

Figure 2.6: ReLU Function

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) = \begin{cases} x_i, & \text{if } x_i \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } x_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad - (1.14)$$

Compared to other AFs (e.g. sigmoid function) ReLU effectively eliminates the possibility of a vanishing gradient, ReLU is most commonly implemented in object detection

CNNs [34] and as it does not compute exponentials or division ReLU is far more computationally efficient than other AFs [22]. The standard implementation of ReLU does suffer from some performance issues, ReLU is prone to overfitting compared to sigmoid function [27] though this issue can be resolved with the introduction of a dropout. Additionally, ReLU can cause a reduced optimisation in the loss function during the training process which leads to an error in neuron weight updates thus hindering the learning process. This can be resolved with the implementation of Leaky ReLU which introduces a negative slope thus maintaining weight updates. In the case of an object detection, CNN ReLU is often paired with the softmax function, this function is used to compute probability from an input as a value from 0 - 1 as given below:

Figure 2.7: Softmax Function

$$f(x_i) = \frac{\exp(x_i)}{\sum_j \exp(x_j)} \quad - (1.12)$$

The difference between softmax and sigmoid function is that a softmax function is exclusively used for multi-classification tasks rather than binary tasks.

2.2 Object Detection Methods

The localisation and classification of objects within an image is a complex task, object detection methods fall primarily into 2 distinctive types: region proposal (R-CNNs), and regression algorithms (YOLO). Simpler models were more likely to use the sliding window approach to perform object detection task, however, these methods have been outperformed by the object/region proposal methods[7]. Sliding window algorithms operate by applying a window of a predefined size (n x n) iteratively to a test scene, this window slides in increments of size n applying the model each time. The model will search for a positive instance of a detectable object within this window returning the location of the object that's predicted score is the greatest/surpasses a threshold (often IoU). This

method does not scale effectively with larger input data becoming both resource-heavy and time-consuming [8], to counter this region/object proposal methods have been developed to streamline the detection process. The fundamental idea of an RCNN is to predict the positive existence of all target object within a given input from which the classification and localisation tasks are performed [40]. R-CNN utilise a Region Proposal Network (RPN) which takes an input of any size and outputs a set of object proposal regions each with an associated 'objectness' score which represents the probability of a correct label prediction within this region.

2.2.1 mAP and AP Metrics

The top performing object detectors for the PASCAL and ImageNet dataset both use detection proposal methods achieving high level of detection and classification accuracy. An understanding of the performance metrics is required to run a comparative analysis on object detection algorithms, mean Average Precision is the most commonly used performance metric for R-CNN and SSD performance analysis [11]. To calculate mAP first the AP (average precision) must be calculated this metrics has three key componets, the IoU, precission, and recall.

IoU (Intersection over union) represents the area of intersection and union between a predicted BB and the ground truth BB and is used as the primary evaluation a models ability to generate an accurate BB.

Precision denoted as $\text{precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ where TP represents the true positive with an IoU of > 0.5 where a correct label prediction has been made, and FP represents false positive with an IoU of 0 or < 0.5 or where duplicate BBs are present is used to measure the percentage of correct predictions. Finally recall which is denoted as $\text{recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$.

To find the AP (average precision) a precision-recall curve is plotted using the latter metrics, the AP defined as the area below this curve is collected from a normalised version of this data. Finally the mAP is calculated from the average AP of all class definition, there are permutations of this approach such as interloped AP, COCO AP, and PASCAL

AP but all follow the same framework [6]. For binary classification tasks it may only be necessary to calculate the AP depending on the number of significant labels.

2.2.2 R-CNNs

Early R-CNNs such as those developed by J.R.R. Uijlings et al utilised semantic segmentation and selective searching to refine class predictions. A primary issue with many detection algorithms was their inability to detect objects at varying scales and objects with less clear boundaries, as such, there was no optimal strategy for the grouping of regions within an image [19]. Selective searching with hierarchical grouping was implemented as an alternative to exhaustive searching which functions by segmenting an image into a collage of minor regions and aggregating them together with hierarchical grouping 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Selective hierarchical grouping

This produces a smaller selection of regions that are more likely to contain an ob-

ject. This approach challenges the computational inefficiencies of many object detection algorithms and removes the computation bottleneck that was inherent in this domain. High-performance R-CNNs have achieved mAP of 62.4% on PASCAL datasets and 31.4% on ImageNet placing them within the top 3 best performing object detection algorithms [9] [19]. R. Girshick expanded on this idea with the introduction of Fast R-CNN (FR-CNN) which aimed to reduce the computation necessary to analyse region proposals. FR-CNN introduces an RoI pooling layer which aimed to reduce the spatial dimensionality of feature maps, backpropagation is also specialised in this model to increase the streamlining of the model during each epoch. This type of R-CNN achieved far higher mAP on test datasets with 70% on PASCAL dataset [18].

Though FR-CNN managed to greatly improve the performance of object detection tasks it still used selective searching which was a computationally expensive process. It wasn't until S. Ren and al. introduced region proposal networks (RPN) which utilise anchor boxes to localise object within an image that CNNs managed to jump this hurdle [31]. Anchor boxes refined the detection process by applying fixed-sized BB to the whole image the detection problem is then broken down into two generalised steps: does a class occur within this BB? What adjustments are necessary to fit this predicted class? ROI (region of interest pooling) is then applied to extract the class features which are output as a new tensor. Faster R-CNNs achieved a mAP of 78% on the pascal 2007 dataset though they still struggled with real-time object detection.

2.2.3 YOLO

YOLO algorithms are characterised by their ability to perform BB and class probability prediction in a single pass through the NN thus the name 'You Only Look Once', the various YOLO architectures provide high performance static and real-time object detection with low computational costs. YOLO utilises non-maximum suppression (NMS) to optimise class probability predicting by refining the number of BB predictions in the final layers of the model which acts to aggregate overlapping BB of the same class [30]. This

optimised architecture performed making them much faster than R-CNNs with selective searching as it operates as a single cohesive process chain, this optimisation resulted in more precise BB prediction with YOLO on average creating 98 BB per image vs 2000 when an R-CNN was trained on the same dataset. When applied to the PASCAL dataset YOLO was capable of achieving a similar mAP to FR-CNN (63.4% vs 70.0% respectively) [30] though YOLO managed to achieve this score on real-time data (45 fps vs 0.5 fps). Later iterations of YOLO i.e. YOLO9000/v2 is capable of performing real-time object detection on 9000 object categories, this algorithm introduced batch normalisation which removed the need for further regularisation on the model architecture [29]. This increased the mAP by an additional 2% making it one of the highest performing object detection algorithms.

2.3 Data Augmentation

An effective neural network relies heavily on big data to achieve greater accuracy, the latter is a well established principle of machine learning [37], datasets of smaller sizes can result in a variety of algorithmic inefficiencies such as overfitting. Overfitting refers to the phenomenon in which a NN generalises the dataset during training as to perfectly fit said training set rather than abstract features. Data augmentation allows a far more comprehensive dataset to be constructed from small or bias dataset where collating data can be difficult. Such difficulties are especially prevalent in the field of medicine where the collection of large dataset is labour intensive, expensive, and ethically grey.

Figure 2.9: Geometric DA

Powerful image analysis is in high demand in medicine as demonstrated by Esteva et al [17] study on skin cancer and liver lesion classification demonstrated by Litjens et al [24] this problem is not so prevalent in certain fields of geospatial data analysis where vast datasets can be collated from opensource repositories. Data augmentation must include translational invariances in the permuted dataset such that the resulting model is able to handle these challenges [?]. Such invariances include; viewpoint, occlusion, lighting, background, scale etc. 'Traditional' data augmentation techniques such as geometric transformation ensure such invariances are sustained in the new dataset these include colour space augmentation, image transformation, and cropping, this form of geometric transformation can be safely applied to image datasets where recognition of a label is not dependant on orientation i.e. cats and dogs Vs numerical digits. Generally geometric transformation refers to the alteration of the geometry of an image by mapping individual pixel values to new destinations, this process preserves the class representation of the image but changes it orientation [39]. In task where label preservation is important it is crucial to observe how the training data is being permuted and to ensure such methods are appropriate for the domain. Image flipping is the most common form of geometric transformation as it is easy to implement and computationally effective. This transformation applies a simple rotation by remapping the each pixel (x, y) to $(x1, y1)$ with the following transformation 2.10, rotations of $-/+ 30$ degrees have been shown to be substantial enough to generate new invariant samples [39].

Figure 2.10: Rotation Example

Satellite imagery introduces additional invariances such as atmospheric cloud cover

and illumination that must also be included in the new dataset. The latter is what makes it difficult to implement a generalised approach for data augmentation as such transformations are domain-dependant. Geometric transformation or 'instance-based augmentation' [?] are commonly applied to satimage datasets in task ranging from object detection to super resolution. The benefit of data augmentation on image classification tasks is clearly demonstrated by Moreno-Barea et al [26] this study trained a 5 layer CNN on the CIFAR-10 dataset first without data augmentation then using a rotation transformation yielding in increased accuracy of 6.3 percent. As well as being simple to implement such transformation are effective in dataset where a positional bias is present e.g. facial recognition, the trade off is an increase in training time and memory usage.

Colour space transformation or photometric transformation is especially effective against the invariances seen in image recognition problems. Photometric transformations can be implemented in various ways yet they all follow the same logic, image data is encoded into 3 stacked matrices consisting of individual RGB pixel values therefore all transformations act to alter these pixel values to lighten, darken, or isolate certain aspect of an image by shifting pixel values (r,g,b) to (r1,g1,b1). A common form of photometric transformation is greyscaling which is used to produce a simplified representation of image data by producing a single layer matrices, however, this transformation was found to reduce classification accuracy by 3 percent on ImageNet, PASCAL, and VOC datasets [1].

Experiments conducted using various transformation methods by AUTHOR et al using the Caltech101 dataset showed the benefit of geometric transformation in CNN model performing image recognition tasks, these testes showed that in all cases the application of DA improved the overall performance of the CNN with geometric transformation outperforming photometric transformation in this specific recognition task [39] though this is likely due to this datasets containing invariances of geometry rather than lighting or colour. Cropping yielded the greatest increase in accuracy with in increase of 13.82 percent from the baseline test likely due to the increased number of permutation this form of augmentation can produce thus creating a larger augmented dataset. Though

AUTHOR et al have conducted thorough testing they have not produced data on the effect of combining various DA methods which may provide a greater increase in performance. As with traditional geometric transformations, photometric transformation has the trade off of increase training time and resource cost, additionally some methods of photometric transformation may alter or discard crucial RGB data preventing the transformation from preserving the labels. This is especially true where label recognition is colour dependent as is common in both geospatial and medical image data analysis [43].

Figure 2.11: Geometric DA vs Photometric DA

	Top-1 Accuracy	Top-5 Accuracy
Baseline	48.13 ± 0.42%	64.50 ± 0.65%
Flipping	49.73 ± 1.13%	67.36 ± 1.38%
Rotating	50.80 ± 0.63%	69.41 ± 0.48%
Cropping	61.95 ± 1.01%	79.10 ± 0.80%
Color Jittering	49.57 ± 0.53%	67.18 ± 0.42%
Edge Enhancement	49.29 ± 1.16%	66.49 ± 0.84%
Fancy PCA	49.41 ± 0.84%	67.54 ± 1.01%

2.4 Image Intelligence - IMINT

IMINT is a discipline of intelligence gathering that uses an array of mediums to produce and analyse images, this study will focus on the medium of satellite and aircraft. The discipline of IMINT often intersects with the discipline of geospatial data analysis thus this field is often referred to as GEOINT, the application of IMINT has long been valued by state institutions. During the 1800s IMINT was used in the American Civil War to record the positions of enemy combatants and fortifications though this yielded little success. When film and camera technology advance so did the capabilities of this form of intelligence gathering. IMINT was used widely during both WW1 and WW2 for strategic and tactile purposes with the technology of the time allowing the military to collect vast amounts of information. Most famously, IMINT truly came to prominence during the cold war when specialised aircraft and later satellites were developed specifically for IMINT

gathering. The U-2 spy plane, one of the first of its kind, provided the American military with key intelligence such as that gathered during the infamous Cuban missile crisis of 1962. IMINT provides concrete information on infrastructure, installations, and terrain and is crucial to the military in OOB and BDA analysis, developing target intelligence, and enemy course of action assessments.

Figure 2.12: Soviet missiles in Cuba - image taken from an USAF U-2

The dawn of the modern era brought great advancement in innumerable scientific disciplines, the proliferation of electro-optic sensors [32] and the focus on aerospace technologies led to the advent of UAVs, SAR, and bespoke imaging satellites. Reconnaissance is the most prolific form of IMINT being used for geographical, meteorological, and military purposes0 though military and state intelligence organisations conduct the most complex forms of IMINT gathering that pose unique challenges and limitations.

2.4.1 IMINT Systems and Sensors

Both satellite and airborne IMINT can be collected from a range of commercial, civil, and governmental systems with each providing different limitations and advantages. For example, commercial satellites can often provide a higher resolution image and can be shared with allies without exposing capabilities [35] whereas government-owned satellite systems are often equipped with a wider range of sensors that have specific IMINT gather

Figure 2.13: RAF MQ-9A Reaper Drone

capabilities. Similarly, government/military airborne IMINT collection systems have a wider range of capabilities and the advantage of being deployed at the theater/tactical level, additionally UAVs are capable of remaining airborne for longer than commercial Intelligence Surveillance Reconnaissance (ISR) systems which are often used for civil purposes rather than military [30]. Given the necessity of continuous observation, battlefield surveillance is conducted using aircraft such as JSTARS and UAVs [20] rather than satellites which will only cover an area of interest for some time as imaging satellites often aren't geostationary. Both airborne and satellite systems can be configured with a range of electronic, optical, electro-optical, chemical, or mechanical sensors, this study will focus sensors capable of image data collection. Imaging sensors can generally be categorised as electro-optical (EO) or radar both provide different capabilities that are suited for different forms of intelligence collection.

EO sensors are characterised by their passive sensing abilities meaning they produce an image by capturing reflected or emitted electromagnetic energy with each part of the EM spectrum producing a different representation of the target area or object. This form of IMINT collection is especially useful in covert scenarios as it lowers the chances of the target of detecting that reconnaissance is being conducted [7], the trade-off is that EO sensors are susceptible to adverse weather, lighting, and atmospheric conditions [35]. Each EO sensor provides unique IMINT collection capabilities that can provide effective insight

Figure 2.14: Landsat 8 imaging satellite

into an array of situations and target areas. Infrared (IR) and thermal infrared (TIR) utilise the infrared portion of the EM spectrum to detect heat and radiation. In a civil application, this technology can provide crucial information pertaining to the management of agriculture and water resources with military applications ranging from tracking missile fire to the movement and build-up of troops [12]. Overhead persistent infrared (OPIR) combined infrared with multiple other EO sensors to conduct persistent surveillance of a target area. This form of surveillance allows an organisation to detect energy from both tactical and strategic targets whilst characterising these emissions as an event or process [35].

Radar sensors are characterised by their active scanning abilities as they emit energy and make inferences based on how this energy is reflected. Unlike EO sensors, radar is not susceptible to weather conditions as such can be deployed in virtually any environment [10]. Synthetic-Aperture Radar (SAR) is a very prolific form of radar sensor for both satellite and aerial imagery that operated by using the platform's flight path to simulate a large antenna or aperture thus 'synthetic-aperture'. The SAR sensors will produce multiple emissions over a target area and record the returned pulses (backscatter) electronically, this method allows SAR to have a far better azimuth resolution compared to most EO sensors making it especially suited to intelligence collection [8]. The electronic data is then processed and present in a human-readable format ??, this process is complex taking

Figure 2.15: Synthetic Aperture Radar geometry

into consideration factors such as the angle of incidence and the Doppler effect. The application of either radar or EO sensors remains domain-specific, however, SAR does provide advanced capabilities unachievable to EO. SAR is capable of penetrating through obfuscating layers e.g. ice, vegetation, tree canopy [11] SAR is also more capable of observing the movement of targets within a given area thus its implementation in change detection e.g. vehicle movement, ice monitoring, crop harvest, flood mapping.

There were over 8300 satellites in orbit as of 2018 with over 150 of those being earth imaging satellites [5]. This number is expected to increase greatly with plans by private space-tech companies such as SpaceX to launch an additional 40,000 satellites. It is theorised that there are enough earth imaging satellites in orbit to produce and entirely new image of the earth surface every week and so the need to find new and intuitive ways to process this unique and challenging form of big data is paramount.

2.5 Geospatial Data Analysis and Machine Learning

Geospatial data refers to an object, event, or phenomena that has a location on the surface of the earth either static (e.g. mountain range, poverty indexes) or dynamic (e.g.

Figure 2.16: SAR image

vehicle in motion, spread of a disease). The analysis of such data often combines location data with attribute (event/ object characteristics) and temporal data (time/duration of occurrence). Geospatial data analysis has far ranging applications from tracking SDGs and poverty indexes to the tracking of maritime vessels or the monitoring of eco-diversity. The recent proliferation of low-cost satellite and the availability of vast opensource satimg datasets combined with advancements in computing, mathematics, and statistical analysis has aided in the proliferation of this form of data analysis and the formation of GIS. Like all fields of analytical science GIS is now faced with the challenge of processing immense datasets in ways that allow the full richness of data to be extract, machine learning has been used to resolve many of the problems big data presents with geospatial data analysis being no exception.

2.5.1 Operational Damage Assessment

One field of GDA where machine learning has already made an impact is the field of Operational Damage Assessment (ODA), this is the practice of estimating the damage

sustained during a natural or man-made disaster as the ascertain the necessary amount of financial and humanitarian aid to assign for recovery. Traditionally ODA employs the "boots on the ground" approach where damage is assessed by large teams which can be both times consuming and expensive, such methods were employed in a range of notorious natural disasters such as the boxing day tsunami of 2004 [38]). A study carried out by Novikov et al evaluated the benefit of using machine learning as an ODA tool to asses structural damage to neighborhoods damaged during the Ventura fires of 2017 - 2018. This study employed the use of semantic segmentation in a CNN to observe changes in the class label of a given area. Semantic segmentation is used to associate each pixel within an image to a class label (e.g. car, person, building, etc) a technique that is used in application ranging from automated driving to medical imaging. This model used open-source images of the disaster area both pre and post-event to evaluate the extent of damage 2.17.

Figure 2.17: Change detection with semantic segmentation

The model took a matter of hours to train on unique datasets and was able to detect changes with an accuracy of 0.89, from this analysis an ODA was able to produce a preliminary assessment of the disaster in 3 hours versus the average workflow time of 2 days (on a disaster of this scale). This approach provided a rapid response, accurate intelligence, and a greater level of efficiency versus traditional methods.

2.5.2 Socio-economic Evaluations

The field of socioeconomic is one of great complexity due to the range and ambiguity of the metrics used to perform these assessments, additionally these surveys often struggle to obtain a granular picture of poverty as such studies often producing inaccurate data leading to the miss-allocation of resources. A study conducted by Isabelle Tingzon et al investigated how machine learning could be combined with GDA to produce a more accurate poverty map of the Philippines. The Philippines was chosen as the study target due to both its high level of poverty and its challenging geography, the high level of vegetation combined with concentrated areas of population creates a unique challenge for a ML model. Again the team used a CNN to develop a model that could identify a range of labels to be used as poverty index metrics these included, nighttime luminosity, urbanisation, access to water etc, with statistical data such as access to education and wealth index to name a few. The CNN performed classification on over 1000 labels to produce a fine grain analysis of spatial data, the team were able to produce a complete poverty map of the Philippines 2.18. The paper falls short of evaluating the accuracy of their findings though it does however prove the versatility of ML enable GDA.

Figure 2.18: Ground truth poverty map of the Philippines archipelago

Chapter 3

Model Development

As mentioned in the methodology multiple prototypes were developed on order to critically analyse which technologies proved most viable for the classification task with each prototype aiming to test 3 key aspect: data manipulation, training optimisation, and detection optimisation. A variety of datasets were used to test various machine learning implementations, this ensured that the algorithm would not generalise its pattern detection and could, in future, be effectively retrained for purposes beyond this specific domain. These prototypes also aimed to implement a range of technologies intended to increase multiple aspect of the model performance from optimising the objective function to streamlining the normalisation and preparation of data. Data taken from airborne and spaceborne sensors has been utilised in the latter implementations, these model have been exclusively trained on EO sensor data specifically photographic data due to the availability of this data.

3.1 Lab Specifications

All elements of prototype development were conducted on a desktop computer with the following specifications:

Processor	i7-4790 3.60GHz (8 core)
Graphic Cards	Nvidia GTX 970
RAM	16GB

Keras and tensor-flow python packages were used in the development of models v1 and v2 with the darknet C/CUDA framework being implemented in prototype v3.

3.2 Model Prototype v1: Binary Classification with CNN

The initial prototype was developed to test how a CNN performed when running a binary classification task against limited image data as well as how performance could be improved with the use of data augmentations and dropout. Yifan Li et al study on [23] shows that deep learning approaches outperform other neural network structures in image classification. Yifan Li et al's comparison of various NN implementations demonstrated that when performing a image classification task CNNs have a far lower MSE (Mean Squared Error) by the final epoch [21] this was especially evident in classification tasks performed on geospatial data.

3.2.1 Data Taxonomy

This dataset consists of 25002 images of cats and dogs equally split between the 2 labels, only a small portion of this dataset was used to increase training time and test the impact of various data augmentation and optimisation techniques. The image data are not of a consistent size or shape and show cats and dogs in a variety of orientations and a

variety of breeds. The dataset used for this prototype was source from googles mledu dataset [16].

3.2.2 Data Normalisation and Preparation

This dataset sample consisted of 1000 images of cats and dogs (500 each respectively) with an additional 500 out of sample images for each classification tag. The image data are not all the same dimensionality and as the NN cannot process data of different dimensionalities the data must be normalised. This is achieved by setting all image array sizes to 100 x 100, a random sample of the data is visualised using matplotlib to ensure the normalisation was successful fig 3.1. Though this normalisation may lead to some distortion in the image this will not prevent the NN from identifying trainable features for this data.

Figure 3.1: Dataset sample

For the purpose of this classification task it is unnecessary to pass 3-channel images of this resolution to the network as the detection being performed is not reliant on 3-channel colour so the resolution is lowered and the image is gray-scaled fig 3.2. This is a more computationally efficient way to train this model without reducing model performance. Both datasets (validation and training) are then converted into floating tensors using the pre-existing method provided by the *tf.keras* import.

3.2.3 Model Training

CNNs follows a standard architecture that consist of 3 main building blocks; convolutional layers (Conv2D), pooling layers (MaxPooling2D), and a fully connected layer. The

Figure 3.2: Greyscale image

Figure 3.3: Model Summary

```
Model: "sequential_1"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 150, 150, 16)	448
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 75, 75, 16)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 75, 75, 16)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 75, 75, 32)	4640
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 37, 37, 32)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 37, 37, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 18, 18, 64)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 18, 18, 64)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 20736)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 512)	10617344
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 1)	513

```
Total params: 10,641,441
Trainable params: 10,641,441
Non-trainable params: 0
```

Conv2d layer is the portion of the NN that extracts specific features from image data with the pooling layer reducing the dimensionality of the tensor output to focus on the most important elements, the flatten layer then produces a 'flattened' form of these features which are used by the loss function to make a label prediction on the final layer.

This model was trained over 15 epochs, using ReLU as the activation function and binary cross entropy as the loss function fig 3.4. As show in fig 3.8 the model is overfit-

ting and further data augmentation was necessary to expand the training dataset. Data augmentation techniques have been shown to greatly enhance the performance of a classification task where a small dataset size has resulted in model generalisation, traditional methods of data augmentation have been proven to yield the greatest results where the validation accuracy is used as a metric for comparison [41]. Traditional data augmentation techniques were implemented on the existing data i.e. cropping, rotating, distortion, zooming etc, to increase the dataset size.

Figure 3.4: Binary cross entropy

$$H_p(q) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \cdot \log(p(y_i)) + (1 - y_i) \cdot \log(1 - p(y_i))$$

A dropout of 0.2 was introduced in each layer to better optimise the structure of the CNN this method has been shown to greatly improve the generalisation performance of image classification dataset when compared to NN that had not introduced drop out [36]. Dropout performed exceptionally well when combined with rectified linear unites (ReLU) show a decrease in error from 1.60 % to % 0.94 when applied to a similar size CNN using the MNIST data set [36]. The ReLU activator was already present within the CNN but with the introduction of both data augmentation and dropout there was a significant increase the in CNNs performance [36]. The final epoch achieved a accuracy of an 0.95 and a loss of 0.12.

Figure 3.5: Augmented model

Figure 3.6: Model Overfitting

3.3 Model Prototype v2: Object Detection

With a clear strategy for data optimisation established the model can be progressed to include more expansion object detection capabilities. This model will provide both localisation and classification by implementing the sliding window approach, this will allow the study to evaluate the performance of implementing a simple object detection algorithm on a binary classification task before progression onto more complex multi-classification and localisation. This model will also transition to a new form of data as this model will be trained and tested on open-source satellite image data.

3.3.1 Data Taxonomy

This model was trained on 2 datasets, the first consists of 4000 image chips collected over the San Francisco Bay Area, The image chips have been categorised into classes for both training and validation 3.7. The images tagged "ship" consists of 1000 80x80 near-center images of ships in various orientations, size, and atmospheric cloud cover. A further 3000 images of 80x80 labelled "no-ship" consists of 3 different classifications, the first 3rd of this classification consists of images of random land coverage e.g. water, vegetation, bare

earth, and buildings. The next 3rd of consists of 80x80 partial images of ships these are portions of a ship that are not significant enough to meet the model classification. The remaining portion consists of commonly mislabeled images containing strong linear features or high pixel brightness know as confusers. The sample also contained full-frame visual scenes which are orthorectified to a 3-meter pixel size [41]. The second consist of 32000 images chips of aircraft in the same configuration, 1/4 of the images hold the "plane" class and the remaining 3/4 are in the "no-plane" class. Again this dataset consists of data with a range of dynamic invariances and "confusers". Both dataset were sourced from Planet's Open California dataset.

Figure 3.7: Training data sample

3.3.2 Data Normalisation and Preparation

More complex data normalisation and pre-processing techniques were implemented in this prototype to ensure the best possible performance of the model. The vector representation of the images are first converted into a 4-dimensional numpy array with the label also being converted to a single dimension numpy array of integer values corresponding to the images classification types (e.g. 1 = ship 0 no-ship), the digital information of each image

is then visualised. The image vectors are then converted to a binary matrix representation. As is standard practise the index was then shuffled before training, this ensures that each training iteration serves a subset of the training data to the model which better optimises the output of the loss function.

3.3.3 Model Training and Architecture

Figure 3.8: Model Summary

```

Model: "sequential"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
conv2d (Conv2D)             (None, 20, 20, 32)         896
-----
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D) (None, 10, 10, 32)         0
-----
dropout (Dropout)           (None, 10, 10, 32)         0
-----
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)           (None, 10, 10, 32)         9248
-----
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2 (None, 5, 5, 32)         0
-----
dropout_1 (Dropout)         (None, 5, 5, 32)          0
-----
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)           (None, 5, 5, 32)          9248
-----
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2 (None, 2, 2, 32)         0
-----
dropout_2 (Dropout)         (None, 2, 2, 32)          0
-----
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)           (None, 2, 2, 32)          102432
-----
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2 (None, 1, 1, 32)         0
-----
dropout_3 (Dropout)         (None, 1, 1, 32)          0
-----
flatten (Flatten)           (None, 32)                 0
-----
dense (Dense)               (None, 512)                16896
-----
dropout_4 (Dropout)         (None, 512)                0
-----
dense_1 (Dense)             (None, 2)                  1026
-----
Total params: 139,746
Trainable params: 139,746
Non-trainable params: 0
-----

```

This model prototype aims to expand on the models functionality by introducing object detection and classification with a sliding window CNN. The progression from a simpler binary classification task will allow the model to be implemented on a far larger scale, the implementation of an sliding window approach utilises a sliding frame to analyse

the whole image by segmenting it into 20x20 pixel regions and applying bound boxes where a target label is found. This model did not utilise proposed regions which may have been a contributing factor the performance issues found with this model. As with the previous binary classification model a sequential structure has been used, this allows the network to be constructed in linear stack of layers by using the `.add()` method. The model consists of an initial Conv2D input layer which receives input shape information, this step is only necessary on the initial layer as successive layers perform automatic shape inference. The models consists of another 7 layers (4 MaxPooling2D 3 Conv2D layers) with an additional dropout of 0.25 after each MaxPooling2D. Before training the learning process must be configured using the `compile method()` where the loss function, optimiser, and metrics need to be set. The loss function represents the objective the model will attempt to minimize, for this model we have used categorical cross entropy which is used for single label categorisation, this loss function measures the performance of a classification model where the output is a probability value between 0 and 1 and the loss increases as the predicted probability diverges from the observed label.

Figure 3.9: Categorical Cross Entropy Loss Function

$$CCE(p, t) = - \sum_{c=1}^c t_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c})$$

For the optimiser, SGD (Stochastic gradient descent optimizer) was used as one of the most common and best performing gradient descent optimisation algorithms. Black box optimisers such as SGD are commonly used with models with a less precise objective function or where the objective cannot be found exactly as is the case with this model.

Much research was conducted on the most appropriate activation and optimisation function for this model, ReLU mathematically defined as ($y = \max(0, x)$) is the most commonly used activation function for CNNs and combined with the softmax classification

Figure 3.10: Stochastic gradient descent optimizer

$$V_t = \beta V_{t-1} + \alpha \nabla_w L(W, X, y)$$

$$W = W - V_t$$

function. The activation function is applied to the hidden layers of a DNN to introduce non-linearity to the model allows the model to perform more complex tasks on complex data. For this metric "accuracy" was used as this is a classification task thus observing the number of correct predictions as a fraction of the total number of input samples is the most appropriate function fig ???. In multi classification task it may be more suitable to use a logarithmic loss function as accuracy function can provide false sense of accuracy during the miss-classification of minor classes.

Figure 3.11: Rectified Linear Unit

Once compiled the model can be trained using the `.fit()` method, again a number of parameters are passed to this method to configure the model. First, the input (x) and target (y) data are passed to the method as a numpy arrays followed by the batch size. This hyperparameter is passed as a integer values that denotes the number of samples propagated through the network per gradient update. This model experimented with

both mini-batch GD and SGD with SGD being selected as the preferred optimisation approach as such the hyperparameter is set to 32 with an epoch of 50. The validation split is then set to 0.2 denoting that 20 percent of the dataset will be used as validation data, this means the model will not train on this data rather using it to evaluate the performance metrics at the end of each epoch. This validation set is selected from the last sample of both the x and y data after shuffling has occurred. As with the previous model the training data is shuffled between each epoch by setting the shuffle parameter to True, shuffling is another method of optimising the loss function by presenting a unique set of training samples to each iteration preventing the loss function getting stuck at a local minimum and thus helping to prevent overfitting. The model achieved a final accuracy of 0.96 for dataset A and a final accuracy of 0.97 for dataset B

3.4 Final Model: Multi Classification with YOLOv3

With the model now capable of performing localisation and binary classification the study can progress to include multi-classification on more complex data. This model will utilise the YOLO darknet framework and will be trained on a combination of satellite and aerial images of varying GSDs.

3.4.1 Dataset Taxonomy

Due to limitation in available data, changes to the models capabilities had to be made. The acquisition of a large enough image dataset of military vehicles was no possible due to the nature of the data, as such an alternative multi-classification dataset was used. The implementation of this model trained on the this dataset still demonstrated the ability for a IMINT ML tool to perform a localisation and classification task that could be retrained to learn any set of labels and classifications. This model was trained using DOTA (Data set for Object Detection in Aerial Images) [42] which consists of 2806 satellite and aerial images from an array of sensors and platforms (e.g. Google Earth) with 188282 individual object instances. The images range in size from 800 x 800 to 4000 x 4000 and so data normalisation was necessary with this dataset. An array of invariances have been included in this dataset with object being presented in various scales, orientations and shaped with additional domain specific in-variances. Compared to other large object detection datasets DOTA provides a larger array of complex scene ensure a greater performance in real-world applications. There are 16 categories within the DOTA dataset (plane, ship, storage tank,baseball diamond, tennis court, basketball court, ground track field, harbor, bridge, large vehicle, small vehicle, helicopter, roundabout, soccer ball field and basketball court)

3.4.2 Data Preparation and Normalisation

DOTA cannot be used fresh out the box and so various manipulation must be applied to the data before it can be passed to the model for training. TO being the dataset must be split into ta training set, validation set, and testing set using a python script (split.py). This script randomly selects half of the training dataset as training images, 1/6th as validation images, and 1/3rd as testing images. The scrips also acts to normalise the data for testing by applying a cropping augmentation this separates the images into 1024 x 1024 square images with 0 padding added where necessary. A second script (YOLOtransform.py) is then run to switch the image data files from VOC format to YOLO, these data files contained the coordinates of the ground truth bounding boxes that are used during training.

3.4.3 Model Training and Architecture

Hyper parameter	value
loss	YOLO
optimiser	SGD-Momentum
epochs	50
batch	64
momentum	0.9
decay	0.0005
learning rate	0.001

This model expands greatly on Model v2 with the implementation of multiple technologies. The previous CNN model relied on the sliding window approach for object detection which proved to be both time consuming and inefficient, this model introduces the concept of R-CNNs with the implementation of YOLOv3 (You Only Look Once) based on Xia et al study on aerial observation [42]. This prompted major changes in the architecture of the network which has switched from a traditional CNN architecture to

a 'darknet' architecture which introduces an array of additional network functionalities and layers. Finally, this model has expanded from binary object detection to probabilistic multi-classification allowing for the detection and classification of multiple objects within a given scene.

Darknet is an opensource NN framework written in C and CUDA that enables rapid and versatile object detection capabilities, the structure of darknet differs from that of a standard CNN with the introduction of upsampling layers and residual blocks. As this is a multi-classification task there will naturally be some in-balance between the class labels and so precautions need to be taken to ensure these minority labels are not lost during training, to manage this darknet implements oversampling. Oversampling is the process of duplicating minority class observations to produce a more balanced dataset ensuring these weights are propagated through the network [13]. As discussed in section 2.3 an imbalanced dataset can lead to misreporting of model performance during training and sub-par performance on minority label predictions.

As darknet is a DNN framework with variants such as darknet-19 being 19 layers deep measures must be taken to ensure the learning process remains optimised this darknet implements the residual block method. The logic behind a residual block/skip connection is relatively easy to grasp, where a traditional NN propagates data sequentially through its successive layers a residual block will allow data to skip several layers that may not be useful to the learning process. This tackles an inherent problem with deep networks, though there is a direct correlation between the depth of a network and its performance simply adding layers will not improve model performance. This will likely lead to accuracy saturation and performance degradation residual block aims to tackle this by optimising model learning and allowing a model to dynamically choose how many layers to utilise during training. In a typical NN the model learns the mapping where (x) represents the input:

$$M(x) = y$$

In a NN that implements a residual block instead of using this direct mapping a

residual function is used:

$$f(x) := H(x) - x$$

this prevents the degradation of gradients in deeper networks consisting of multiple non-linear layers.

YOLO's primary difference from a sliding window CNN is its ability to make label predictions on an input from a single pass through the CNN by predicting all bounding boxes from all classes simultaneously. YOLO approaches the detection task differently from standard R/CNNs by framing the task as a regression problem. As opposed to R-CNNs, YOLO observes the entire input image during training as such it is capable of encoding both feature and contextual information when learning class labels this provides a performance advantage over R-CNNs that often struggle with false positives in 'background' data [23]. YOLO performs detection tasks through a method know as unified Detection, the input image is divided into a $S \times S$ grid of cells with each cell responsible for predicting 5 bounding boxes as well as the confidence score which represents the networks certainty that a learned label exists withing that bounding box which is represented as $\Pr(\text{Object}) * \text{IOU truth/prediction}$. Each bounding box has 5 prediction metrics: x, y, w, h , and confidence (x, y) represent the center of a bounding box relative to the bounds of the grid cells and (w, h) represent width and height relative to the whole image. Confidence is a metric representing the IOU of the predicted box and the ground truth box. Each bounding box is also responsible for predicting the conditional class probability C with the probability being conditioned on the existence of an object within the given bounding box. These class-specific confidence scores are calculated using the confidence score and the conditional probability:

$$\Pr(\text{Classi}|\text{Object}) \Pr(\text{Object}) \text{IOU}_{pred}^{\text{truth}} = \Pr(\text{Classi}) \text{IOU}_{pred}^{\text{truth}}$$

The resultant score shows both the probability of a bounding box containing a class label as well as how well the bounding box fits the class prediction. Depending on the spatial resolution of the input image and the instances of a class label YOLO could make any number of predictions, these predictions are filtered using a threshold to ensure

only class prediction => the threshold are shown in the final output. Though it differs between versions, this implementation of YOLO uses both linear and nonlinear activation functions with a liner function implemented on the final layer and a variation of leaky-ReLU implemented on all other layers.

Figure 3.12: Leaky ReLU function

$$\phi(x) = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0.1x, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

YOLO implements a unique multi-part loss function to tackle the stability issues inherent with the object detection model. As the entire image is passed through the CNN multiple grid cells will not contain a label classification as such this causes the confidence score of these grid cells is pushed towards 0 resulting in a balanced gradient to cells that do contain a class label. To tackle this loss from bounding box coordinate prediction is increased whilst confidence prediction for bounding boxes that do not contain an object is increased denoted as λ_{coord} , λ_{noobj} .

Figure 3.13: YOLO Multi-pass Loss Function

$$\begin{aligned} & \lambda_{coord} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{obj} \left[(x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \right] \\ & + \lambda_{coord} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{obj} \left[(\sqrt{w_i} - \sqrt{\hat{w}_i})^2 + (\sqrt{h_i} - \sqrt{\hat{h}_i})^2 \right] \\ & \quad + \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{obj} (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2 \\ & \quad + \lambda_{noobj} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{noobj} (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2 \\ & \quad \quad + \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \mathbb{1}_i^{obj} \sum_{c \in \text{classes}} (p_i(c) - \hat{p}_i(c))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$\mathbb{1}_i^{obj}$ denotes the occurrence of an object in a cell and $\mathbb{1}_{ij}^{obj}$ denotes the jth bounding box predictor in cell i is responsible for the latter prediction, the later portions of the loss function are responsible for implementing the conditional penalisation as previously

discussed. Additional hyperparameters were configured with this model to fine-tune the more complex learning process. A high momentum of 0.9 has been set with the SGD loss function optimiser to ensure the loss function does not become stuck at a local minimum. A lower decay and learning rate ensures a more rigid learning process this prevents minor class labels from being discarded during training.

Chapter 4

Model Evaluation & Discussion

4.1 Evaluation

The evaluation of each model version consisted of a critical comparison of the models capabilities against the predetermined aims of this study as well as an assessment of the measurable and observable metrics defined in the hypothesis. This method allowed this study to ensure the model was performing to the specifications it had set out to fulfill whilst ensure the general performance of the model in its objective function was of a high level. The evaluation of each model consisted of testing its performance against the associated test data, as all model versions are performing object detection the first observable metric was the models ability to perform localisation and classification on the trained labels within a given input. This performance index was given as a percentage of the detected objects against the number of detectable objects within the input scene/batch, consideration was also giving for the time it took each model version to perform its task. The output of the loss functions were also recorded during training to evaluate the training process of each model, this was to evaluate the architecture of each model as a reflection of its ability to learn the target data.

4.1.1 Model Prototype v1

As shown in **table** the initial architecture of the model did not perform well during training and thus a dropout was introduced and further data augmentation was applied to the training data. Once data augmentation had been applied and dropouts introduced into the model an increase in performance was observed both during training and when implementing the model against test images. The model was able to successfully predict 100% of the labels of multiple test images without incident included edge cases where a high level of invariance was present. The model was able to perform detection on a singular image in < 1 second this is an acceptable time for a simple binary classification task on images of a lower spatial resolution. This model highlights the importance of having adequate testing, training, and validation data to ensure the model is able to learn generalised features as well as the importance of an optimised model structure. As this paper aims to develop a model where certain domain specific task may present a deficit of data it is important to establish the correct way to challenge and resolve these issues.

4.1.2 Model Prototype v2

As previously mentioned this model was applied to the test scene using a sliding window approach such that the model was applied iteratively to the testing scene in 30×30 sections for the maritime model (model A) and 20×20 for the aircraft model (model B). When model A was applied to a 1800×2700 test scene a high level of classification accuracy was observed with a AP of +70%, as shown in fig 4.1 there were only 3 false-positives observed in the areas of the testing scene containing strong linear features and only 2 false-negatives on smaller vessels without distinctive label characteristics. Even with this incident of error this model has correctly predicted a vast number of label classifications as such that model acts as proof that RCNNs can be effectively applied to geospatial data for object detection tasks.

Varying results were observed when model B was applied to its test scene, when applied

Figure 4.1: Ship Object Detection

to scene 1 almost all instances of an identifiable object were missed achieved a negligible AP $<10\%$ these results were consistent when the model was applied to similar scenes. The irregular occurrence of a correct label prediction did suggest that this could be a spatial issue and not an problem with the model, this is further supported by the metrics observed during training **table** and the models performance during batch testing.

The challenges posed by spatial resolution are more prominent with satellite IMINT than aerial imaging due to greater variance in image quality. Within the field of IMINT image quality is measured by an array of metrics most importantly image resolution and Ground Sampling Distance (GSD). GSD is the the distance between two consecutive pixel centers measured on the ground this value is directly correspondent to the altitude an image is taken from, the higher the altitude the greater the GSD resulting in a lower spatial resolution. A lower spatial resolution makes it harder to detect an object as many of the identifiable features will become obscured. when model B was applied to an image with a higher spatial resolution a far greater number of detectable object were correctly predicted achieving an AP 65% concluding that the performance of the model is directly dependent on the spatial resolution of the image.

Figure 4.2: Scene 1 detection showing a low level of localisation and detection

Figure 4.3: Scene 2 detection showing a high level of localisation and detection

Model v2 took far longer to implement on test data than model v1, taking between 2-3 hours depending on the resolution of the testing scene. These inefficiencies are common in the sliding window method due to the level of computation required during application. This is a limiting factor for the desired application of this model as within that time the IMINT could become redundant or the surveilled area may have changed. As a result, more computationally effective methods need to be developed to ensure a more rapid

application of the model to the test data. Additionally its may be preferable to train models with dataset containing a greater variance of spatial resolutions alternatively it maybe be necessary to train separate models to perform detection within different GSD ranges.

4.1.3 Final Model

This model was implemented on a collection of scenes intended to test the models performance against an array of invariances and challenges. Scenes with varying spatial resolutions and GSDs were used to assess the models versatility in application, the first test scene fig 4.4 is a 1500 x 1747 image with a GSD of 0.273 shows a medium level of successful detection though multiple smaller object have not been successfully detected.

Figure 4.4: YOLO multi-class detection - GSD:0.273

Test image 2 fig 4.5 with a resolution of RES and a GSD of 0.230 shows a similar level of performance against more prominent objects within the image but a higher level of false negatives against the smaller objects.

Figure 4.5: YOLO multi-class detection - GSD: 0.230

Test image 3 fig 4.7 with a resolution of RES and GSD of 0.134 shows the model performance against a lower quality image, here we see a high level of false negatives against prominent objects.

Figure 4.6: YOLO multi-class detection - GSD: 0.134

As mentioned in section section 2.2 YOLO encounters problems when attempting to detect smaller objects, a problem which has been emphasised by the application domain. As with model v2 a clear problem was observed when testing against images of a lower GSD, the problem is exemplified when model v3 is run against test scenes used in model v2. Here we observed a complete inability for model v3 to perform successful detection. This shows the need for a model to be trained on a wider variety of GSD variants to ensure a more versatile level of application. The final model has observed tremendous improvements in testing times, the sliding window approach took approximately 2 - 3 hours to perform a detection task where as YOLO took a fraction of a second to test a scene of a similar size even the largest test scene within the DOTA training set took

Table 4.1: Model performance evaluation

Model	mAP/AP
Model v1	AP 100%
Model v2	AP 75%
Modelv3	varied on GSD (highest mAP 60%)

aprx. 2 seconds to run the detection model. This final model fulfills all the predetermined aims of the study, it has been successfully trained on geospatial data and is capable of performing a high level of multi-classification with localisation.

Allowances have been given to the constraints on testing parameters i.e. resource availability (processing and data) yet still this model has achieved a high level of performance. This model, unlike its predecessors is capable of being applied to varying domains, in theory, this model could be trained on data from either EO or radar sensors with little to no adaptation to the data normalisation/pre-processing. The primary hindrance to the development of this model was the testing environment, the VM that was set up for testing was sharing lab resources as such running a verbose version of YOLO wasn't practical rather YOLO-tiny was used. More comprehensive implementations of YOLO with its increased number of layers would have likely mitigated the performance issues observed during testing as such this study can confidently suggest that had a larger network been practical to implement a far increased level of performance would have been observed. This can be ratified with a comparison between YOLOv3 performance and that of YOLO-tiny in AUTHOR, observed here is a clear difference in model performance with little divergence between the model architecture beyond its increased depth. The full model architecture can be view in the appendix.

Figure 4.7: Final model process chain

Conclusion

This study has highlighted various areas of interest for future development, the problems and challenges encountered during this study have been more insightful than the successes. It is clear from the final model that spatial resolution plays a big role in the performance of object detection CNNs both during testing and training. Even with very large datasets the model struggled with these invariances and was unable to transition to detection task where the spatial resolution was too dissimilar from the training data. This problem was seldom mentioned in similar papers and shows a clear area for further study. However, This study can conclude that machine learning is an effective method of IMINT analysis with the results showing a high level of accuracy in classification and localisation during both binary and multi-classification tasks. It can also be concluded that certain limitation of spares data can be overcome with the introduction of an optimised model structure and adequate data augmentation. The data analyses by the final model was able to perform such tasks faster than any human and with greater clarity contributing to the notion that effective and rich analysis can and should be conducted using machine learning solutions.

Bibliography

[1]

[2] URL <https://icecreamlabs.com>.

[3] URL <https://cs231n.github.io/convolutional-networks/#fc>.

[4] URL <https://www.freecodecamp.org/news/an-intuitive-guide-to-convolutional-neural->

[5] URL <https://www.geospatialworld.net/blogs/do-you-know-how-many-satellites-earth/>.

[6] . URL <http://host.robots.ox.ac.uk/pascal/VOC/>.

[7] . URL <https://eijournal.com/print/articles/exploring-the-benefits-of-active-vs-passive-spaceborne-systems>.

[8] URL https://earth.esa.int/web/guest/missions/esa-operational-eo-missions/ers/instruments/sar/applications/radar-courses/content-2/-/asset_publisher/qIBc6NYRXfnG/content/radar-course-2-synthetic-aperture-radar.

[9] URL https://d2l.ai/chapter_computer-vision/rcnn.html.

[10] . URL <https://www.iceye.com/satellite-data#C2>.

[11] . URL <https://www.iceye.com/satellite-data#C4>.

[12] URL <https://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/thermal-infrared-sensor-tirs/>.

- [13] URL <https://towardsdatascience.com/applied-deep-learning-part-4-convolutional-neu>
- [14] URL <https://towardsdatascience.com/understand-the-architecture-of-cnn-90a25e244c7>
- [15] 2020. URL <https://towardsdatascience.com/handling-imbalanced-datasets-in-machine-learning-7a0e84220f28>.
- [16] 2020. URL <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/download/details.aspx?id=54765>.
- [17] A. Esteva, B. Kuprel, R. A. Novoa, J. Ko, S. M. Swetter, H. M. Blau, and S. Thrun. Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks. *Nature*, 542(7639):115–118, 2017.
- [18] R. Girshick. Fast r-cnn.
- [19] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, and J. Malik. Region-based convolutional networks for accurate object detection and segmentation. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 38(1):142–158, 2016. doi: 10.1109/tpami.2015.2437384.
- [20] L. G. E. HANLON JR. Imagery intelligence. 2002.
- [21] D. Jaswal, S. Vishvanathan, and S. Kp. Image classification using convolutional neural networks. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 5: 1661–1668, 06 2014. doi: 10.14299/ijser.2014.06.002.
- [22] X. Jiang, Y. Pang, X. Li, J. Pan, and Y. Xie. Deep neural networks with elastic rectified linear units for object recognition. *Neurocomputing*, 275:1132–1139, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.neucom.2017.09.056.
- [23] Y. Li, H. Zhang, Q. Guo, and X. Li. Machine learning methods for ship detection in satellite images. *write down Germany, IEEE*, 2013.

-
- [24] G. Litjens, T. Kooi, B. E. Bejnordi, A. A. A. Setio, F. Ciompi, M. Ghafoorian, J. A. Van Der Laak, B. Van Ginneken, and C. I. Sánchez. A survey on deep learning in medical image analysis. *Medical image analysis*, 42:60–88, 2017.
- [25] A. Mishra. Metrics to evaluate your machine learning algorithm. URL <https://towardsdatascience.com/metrics-to-evaluate-your-machine-learning-algorithm-f10ba6e38234>.
- [26] J. Moreno-Barea, F. Strazzera, J. Jerez, D. Urda, and L. Franco. Forward noise adjustment scheme for data augmentation. 11 2018. doi: 10.1109/SSCI.2018.8628917.
- [27] C. E. Nwankpa, W. Ijomah, A. Gachagan, and S. Marshall. Activation functions: Comparison of trends in practice and research for deep learning. .
- [28] C. E. Nwankpa, W. Ijomah, A. Gachagan, and S. Marshall. Activation functions: Comparison of trends in practice and research for deep learning. .
- [29] J. Redmon and A. Farhadi. Yolo9000: Better, faster, stronger.
- [30] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, and A. Farhadi. You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection.
- [31] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, and J. Sun. Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 39(6):1137–1149, 2017. doi: 10.1109/tpami.2016.2577031.
- [32] D. Robert. Guide to imagery intelligence. *Journal of U.S. Intelligence Studies*, 18(2), 2011.
- [33] S. Sharma and R. Mehra. Implications of pooling strategies in convolutional neural networks: A deep insight. *Foundations of Computing and Decision Sciences*, 44(3): 303–330, 2019. doi: 10.2478/fcds-2019-0016.

- [34] E. A. Smirnov, D. M. Timoshenko, and S. N. Andrianov. Comparison of regularization methods for imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *AASRI Procedia*, 6:89–94, 2014. doi: 10.1016/j.aasri.2014.05.013.
- [35] N. G. spatial Intelligence Agency. *Geospatial Intelligence Basic Doctrine*. 2006.
- [36] N. Srivastava, G. Hinton, A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and R. Salakhutdinov. Dropout: a simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *The journal of machine learning research*, 15(1):1929–1958, 2014.
- [37] C. Sun, A. Shrivastava, S. Singh, and A. Gupta. Revisiting unreasonable effectiveness of data in deep learning era. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, pages 843–852, 2017.
- [38] A. Suppasri, S. Koshimura, F. Imamura, A. Ruangrassamee, and P. Foytong. A review of tsunami damage assessment methods and building performance in thailand. *Journal of Earthquake and Tsunami*, 7:1350036, 12 2013. doi: 10.1142/S179343111350036X.
- [39] L. Taylor and G. Nitschke. Improving deep learning with generic data augmentation. In *2018 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, pages 1542–1547, Nov 2018. doi: 10.1109/SSCI.2018.8628742.
- [40] J. R. R. Uijlings, K. E. A. van de Sande, T. Gevers, and A. W. M. Smeulders. Selective search for object recognition. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 104(2):154–171, 2013. doi: 10.1007/s11263-013-0620-5.
- [41] J. Wang and L. Perez. The effectiveness of data augmentation in image classification using deep learning. *Convolutional Neural Networks Vis. Recognit*, 2017.
- [42] G.-S. Xia, X. Bai, J. Ding, Z. Zhu, S. Belongie, J. Luo, M. Datcu, M. Pelillo, and L. Zhang. Dota: A large-scale dataset for object detection in aerial images. In

Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, pages 3974–3983, 2018.

- [43] Q. You, J. Luo, H. Jin, and J. Yang. Robust image sentiment analysis using progressively trained and domain transferred deep networks. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, AAAI'15, page 381–388. AAAI Press, 2015. ISBN 0262511290.